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EVALUATION OF THE EVEN DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS INFRASTRUCTURE AIMED AT IMPROVING THE ABILITIES OF MASS, AMATEUR AND HIGH-PERFORMANCE ATHLETES: FROM THE POINT OF VIEW OF RESIDENTS OF KUPIŠKIS DISTRICT

Tomas Gabriūnas - Master's Degree Student of the Tourism and Sports Management Study Program of the Lithuanian Sports University;

Sport st. 6, Kaunas, Lithuania.

Email: tomas.gabriunas@stud.lsu.lt

Rimantas Mikalauskas - Associate Professor (Master's thesis supervisor), Department of Sports and Tourism Management of the Lithuanian Sports University.

SUMMARY

Research work was carried out in 2022-2023. A quantitative research method - questionnaire - was chosen for the study. Anonymous questionnaires were created. The sample of the questionnaire survey is composed in such a way that its characteristics reflect the characteristics of the general population, that is, it must be representative. 385 residents of Kupiškis district municipality were interviewed. Respondents were both women and men, regardless of age group, but not younger than 18 years, education, social class.

Keywords: sport, infrastructure, sports activities, sports space.

INTRODUCTION

Every normal nation that cares about its future educates a healthy person, both spiritually and physically. The service of the soul must also grow in the growing body, this is the meaning of physical life. The classical philosophy of ancient Greece did not shy away from emphasizing the inseparable connection between these two principles. This was how the harmony between human and the state, the harmony of the body was defined. [3]

Infrastructure development is very important in developed and developing countries and is a major public policy. [1]

It is very important that good conditions are created in Lithuania for the effective training of athletes, physical activity of the population is increased, sports infrastructure is improved and developed, conditions are created for sports organizations to improve the quality of their activities. [5]

In order to improve the sports infrastructure, we want to ensure equal sports development of infrastructure in the country, to develop sports infrastructure according to clearly defined criteria. To the infrastructure the newly prepared and adapted to today's challenges will also contribute to the improvement of Physical Culture and Sports Sponsorship Fund Law - The Physical Culture and Sports Sponsorship Fund is provided for the opportunity to finance not only the purchase of sports inventory and equipment, but also the physical health of the population activity promotion projects. The program of the Seventeenth Government of the Republic of Lithuania also emphasizes the active inclusion of social groups of vulnerable persons, paying particular attention to children belonging to these groups and the youth. These tasks will be pursued through programs and projects aimed at the most for vulnerable target

groups: the disabled, the elderly, national minorities, etc., taking into account the significant differences between individuals in physical activity and sport socioeconomic and cultural groups. [2] In the Kupiškis district municipality, the culture, education and sports department of the Kupiškis district municipality and the Kupiškis district physical education and sports center are responsible for sports and all related matters.

PURPOSE

To assess the sports infrastructure of the municipality of Kupiškis district from the point of view of the residents of the district.

TASKS:

1. To find out in which sports areas the residents of the municipality of Kupiškis district play sports.
2. Find out what sports are promoted by the residents of the municipality of Kupiškis district.
3. To find out how the residents of the district assess the quality of sports infrastructure in the municipality of Kupiškis district.
4. To find out what kind of sport the residents of the district would like to practice, but the infrastructure is not adapted for it.

RESEARCH METHODS

During the research, the scientific literature was analyzed. Research work was carried out in 2022-2023. A quantitative research method - questionnaire - was chosen for the study. Anonymous (nameless) questionnaires have been completed - in this case, the person who answered remains unknown. [6]

The questionnaire was prepared by the author based on the following literary sources: 1. Damalakaitė E., "The impact of Lithuanian sports heritage on popularizing sports among youth in Kaunas" Master's thesis, Kaunas, 2010; 2. Nagy A., Tobak J., "The role of sport infrastructure: use, references and needs" Debrecen, 2015; 3. Sabaliauskas S., "Educational prerequisites of sportsmen's motivation to achieve high mastery" Doctoral dissertation, Vilnius, 2011. The questionnaire consists of open and closed questions with ordinal measurement scales.

Subjects: residents of Kupiškis district municipality. Respondents were both women and men, regardless of age group, but not younger than 18 years, education, social class. Since 16,356 inhabitants lived in the municipality of Kupiškis district according to the data of 2020, 385 respondents were interviewed in order to evaluate the development of sports infrastructure.

The sample of the questionnaire survey is composed in such a way that its characteristics reflect the characteristics of the general population, that is, it must be representative. For social research, it is recommended to set the sample size based on 5 percent. error [4]. The sample size is determined according to the formula: $n=1/(\Delta^2 + 1/N)$. Where: n – the number of cases in the sample group, N – the general set, Δ – the size of the error.

According to this sample formula, at 95% for reliability with a margin of error of 0.05, 385 visitors had to be interviewed. Calculation of the survey sample of the population engaged in sports activities:

$$n=1/(0.05^2+1/16356)=1/0.0026=384.62=385$$

The answers received from the respondents were processed with Microsoft Office and IBM SPSS Statistics programs.

RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

During the survey, 385 respondents were interviewed. There were questions to which the respondents did not provide answers, but there were no questionnaires that were not completely filled out. Figure 1 shows the distribution of respondents' answers, which sports spaces they choose for their training or sports activities. Most respondents chose the option that they do sports in a gym or club (38%). In second place is at home (17%). A little less than at home, the respondents chose that they do sports in several sports areas (16%). 10 percent of respondents did not provide an answer to this question. 9 percent of respondents play sports on outdoor sports grounds, 6 percent - in parks. 2 percent of the respondents each chose that they do sports with outdoor simulators and in unnamed other sports spaces.

Figure 1. In what areas are sports activities carried out?

As can be seen from the graph (Figure 2), the majority of respondents did not choose the specifically named sport, but another option as the promoted sport. As many as 87 residents chose this option. 42 respondents did not provide an answer to this question. Out of all the respondents, 51 residents of the district chose to do several sports. Among the named sports, the most respondents chose that they promote athletics - 82 respondents. Basketball is in second place - 38 respondents. 22 residents of the district are engaged in cycling. 13 respondents each chose that they promote weightlifting, volleyball and moto-car sports. 11 respondents promote football. 4 respondents are engaged in wrestling, swimming and table tennis. And at least, only 1 respondent noted that they promote outdoor tennis.

Figure 2. The sport is promoted by the residents of the municipality of Kupiškis district.

In order to find out how the residents of the district value the sports infrastructure in the municipality of Kupiškis, they were asked how they value the infrastructure of a specific sport. Summary data of residents' opinions about the entire sports infrastructure are presented in Figure 3. Most of the respondents assessed the condition of the sports infrastructure as satisfactory. 23 percent of respondents think so. A little less, 22 percent, had no opinion at all on this issue. And the same number (22%) of respondents rated the sports infrastructure as in good condition. After 10 percent of all respondents assessed the state of sports infrastructure as bad, excellent or did not give an answer at all. And only 3 percent rated the sports infrastructure as very bad.

Figure 3. Evaluation of the quality of the sports infrastructure of the residents of the municipality of Kupiškis district.

In order to find out what kind of sport the residents of Kupiškis district municipality would like to practice, an open-ended question was asked in the questionnaire. Not all respondents answered this question. Only 78 responses were received, which is only one-fifth of all respondents. Out of all the answers received, the residents of Kupiškis district municipality named swimming as the most desired sport (Figure 4). 32 respondents chose this option. Athletics was named in second place among the choices - 7 respondents. Six respondents would like to do cycling. 5 respondents each noted that they would like to practice beach volleyball, moto-car sports and martial arts, but according to them, the sports infrastructure is not adapted for this. Three respondents each named weightlifting, archery, and group training. Two respondents each would like to play ice hockey and golf. And the following sports received one choice each: tennis, table tennis, baseball, disabled sports and rugby.

Figure 4. Sports that the residents of the district would like to practice, but the sports infrastructure is not adapted to it.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The majority of respondents chose to do sports in a gym or club. The least number of respondents engaged in sports activities chose outdoor simulators and other sports spaces.
2. From the given options for specific sports, the majority of respondents chose that they promote athletics. The least number of respondents, only one, chose to promote outdoor tennis. Out of all possible options, the majority of respondents chose other sports. Several sports are promoted by 51 respondents. And 42 respondents did not provide an answer to this question.
3. Almost a quarter of the respondents rated the state of sports infrastructure in the district as satisfactory. Similarly, the same number, but fewer respondents, rated the sports infrastructure as in good condition. However, the same percentage of respondents did not have an opinion on this issue. And only the smallest part of the respondents rated the sports infrastructure in the municipality of Kupiškis district as in very bad condition.

4. What kind of sports activity would you like to do, but the sports infrastructure in the municipality of Kupiškis district is not adapted to it, was answered by only one fifth of all respondents. Among the most frequently mentioned sports was swimming.

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